

Report on data types used in geophysical, geoarcheological and soil science research

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task 2.1 Data types

A) Introduction

This task was aimed on clarifying with what data we are working. During the discussions in WG3, there was found a possibility to use usually un-applied statistical and mathematical approaches. Due to clarify the situation and what is possible and what is not with the data, we tried to describe what are the data we are working with - numerically, how they are stored, how they are processed and how they can be viewed. We tried to enlist the categories which describe what qualities or characteristics can be appointed to the specific data.

B) Data - what is data; sample; data point; property; categories of workflow / processing

Property: property is measured or wanted physical or (geo)chemical characteristic (e.g. content of P in soil in ppm; voltage; magnetic susceptibility; pH)

Method: vague description of what properties and how are measured, e.g. GPR, magnetometer etc.

Technique: particular measurement technique

Device: particular device for measurement, even for one technique there are many devices from many producers; devices can have different softwares and different formats for data outputs and so on.

Sample: what is measured – one sample produces one number by one measurement for every property

Data point: one particular and unique record in dataset

Dataset: where the data are stored

Data: what we need at the end to work with; information about property obtained from measuring the samples

By data we mean in this report any information obtained by a specific method by measurement of the sample of reality (which according to the sciences of interest is usually some soil / sedimentary / structure body of archaeological context).

There are many ways how to obtain a “data” from device – device usually measures some property and in some cases the measured property is also a “wanted” property, in some cases more computation is needed. In some cases, the software of a device does such computation by default and user is presented only with resulting “wanted” property, in some cases user himself has to do the computation. Therefore, here we present suggested way to describe what we mean by data and what other descriptions we use.

- From device = measured = raw „numbers“, from processing = computed = raw data
 - o This arises from the fact, that in some cases we can work with data directly from the measurement, and in some cases there has to be done some recalculation (resistivity from apparent resistivity)
 - o Work flow:
 - 1) Raw „numbers“
 - We don't have yet what (variable, property) we need
 - 2) correction of errors
 - This is not processing of measured variables, this is more about files management flow

- There can be other info stored in file, if measuring device enables it (like name of sample, depth of sampling, any descriptor needed etc)
 - There can be errors made by mistake
 - There can be also “bad” “measurements”, i.e. bad datapoints in file of results from device, e.g. due to measurement device malfunction
 - We may want to remove the “bad datapoints”
 - We may want to correct mistakes e.g. in descriptors
 - We should store info about these (which datapoints and fields are wrong and why and how they was corrected (changed, removed) in txt file
- 3) re-computation
 - Computing new properties from measured ones
 - E.g. ohmmeters from ohms; resistivity from apparent resistivity
- 4) raw data
 - We have what (variable, property) we need
 - Michel Dabas: raw readable
- 5) transformations, cleaning, filtering
 - Removing outliers, logarithmic and other transformation and so on
 - Calculating missing values
- 6) Application of assumption model or inversion
 - GPR migration
- 7) clean data
 - I can interpret it or statistically analyse and then interpret, I can visualise them and so on

C) Area of science and methods

1) Multicreriality

Some property can be described by more levels of the categories below. E.g. magnetic susceptibility can be measured in the field or in the laboratory, which is also connected to the dichotomy between defined and undefined samples.

D) Data types - categories of measurement characteristics

1) Field measurement, laboratory measurement

This means, where we obtain the data. It has relationship not only to the environment, but also on sample character or preparation. Field technics measure natural soil environment and thus are influenced by variable conditions (weather, moisture and so on). Laboratory technics enable to measure samples prepared according to specified standards. Some of the properties can be measures in both ways, although in such cases they represent different measured reality and the data has to be interpreted in right context (e.g. magnetic susceptibility, pH). Some of the methods can be applied only in one way - e.g. GPR has no meaning and practical way to be applied on laboratory samples...

Laboratory measurement can also perform repeated measurement in same conditions of environment and of sample. Same conditions and same samples in repeated measurement are harder (i.e. almost impossible in principle) to achieve in field measurement.

2) Presumption about reality

Majority of methods have some presumptions about measured reality. Laboratory measurements usually presume that the sample was prepared in specific way. Field measurements and especially geophysics presume many characteristics of measured soils and sediments. Usually these presumptions influence the model on which the device is tested and then applied in real environment.

E.g. GPR presume some specifics about the underground layers of sediments: their depth, material characteristics like granulometry, porosity, water content and so on. It also presumes

that the layers are not tilted. These presumptions influence the model through which the data will be interpreted.

3) *Precision, accuracy, calibration*

These processes have great influence on how the data are obtained, processed and interpreted. They are of importance in both laboratory and field techniques.

4) *Defined/homogeneous sample, undefined/heterogeneous sample*

This means, what we really measure and it is closely related to the dichotomy between field and laboratory measurement. When measuring defined sample, we can specifically describe what part of reality we measured, and it is usually sample homogeneous in its characteristics (not only by sample preparation, but also by natural principle that the closer the points the more similar they appear. In case of many field technics of geophysics, the "samples" (the measured reality giving one data point) are usually not so well defined, they are usually greater in spatial dimensions and they can be comprised of various sedimentary / structural bodies of different characteristics. The measurement then represents some general characteristic of all these characteristics together.

Maybe, defined and undefined are not well chosen descriptors - undefined sample can be also defined by spatial coordinates. The definition is not only linked to spatial definition, but also to characteristics definition. We can well and in detail describe the defined sample. We cannot do it in undefined sample (or we could thoroughly examine it - but it goes against philosophy of many techniques and research - time and cost sparing and also not destructive).

The question of defined / undefined samples is linked to the topic of linking the data obtained by different methods of different characteristics: how to link the data of defined samples (e.g. pH, geochemistry) to those of undefined samples (GPR, magnetometry)?

Figure 1. the difference between defined and undefined sample. Defined sample: measurement is linked to defined spatial coordinates (X_i, Y_i, Z_i) and to the reality well described and more homogeneous. Undefined sample is linked to all coordinates ($X_{1...n}, Y_{1...n}, Z_{1...n}$) and also to all its characteristics together (probably more heterogeneous than in defined sample).

Geophysical methods will probably tend to measure the undefined samples, although there are differences in their spatial precision, with e.g. GPR more precise than EM measurements.

The topic of defined and undefined samples has narrow link to the topic of analysing results of more different methods together and so on – how to link information coming from defined sample to undefined samples?

5) Settings of device

The settings of measuring device influence the “raw numbers” and therefore all the data coming from it. This usually has to be taken into account in processing and interpretation. The possibility of set or change the settings by a user is dependent on specific device.

The example of settings according to the technique and device:

- Portable XRF usually:
 - o time of measurement
 - o voltage of XRF beams
- GPR
 - o Number of antennas
 - o Angle of antennas

- EM
 - o Number of frequencies
- Resistivity
 - o Spacing between electrodes
 - Influence on measured depth

6) *Noise, bias, error source*

Noise can originate in many ways; some of it can be removed during the processing. Some noise can originate from presumption about measured reality which is not true (e.g. tilt of geological layers).

Example of error can be a modern iron object on surface of researched area. Such error produces value which has no link to underground archaeological objects. Such errors should be removed from the data. Such errors are also problem to the topic of analysing data from different methods together, especially when data from methods working with defined and undefined samples has to be merged...

7) *Sample preparation*

This is the case of laboratory measurement methods – samples have to be prepared in some standard way (sieving, drying, grinding, dissolving carbonates and so on). This is also linked to homogeneous character of defined samples vs heterogeneous nature of undefined samples.

8) *Dimensionality of measurement*

Dimensionality of measurement is not dimensions of samples – this is commented in defined / undefined sample. Dimensionality of measurement is focused on how the samples (data points) are located to other in space. That means even in case where sample itself is basically 3D, the measurement is in 3D only if the samples are in 3D: e.g. Magnetometry performed in some area is in 3D only if more horizontal levels are measured.

Specific ways of measurement are horizontal and vertical

Some methods basically measure only in one way (vertical or horizontal) and the other is produced by processing. This is an example of GPR, which basically measures in vertical

profiles. Horizontal data (or maps, visualisation etc.) are produced secondarily by slicing these vertical profiles.

E) Data types – categories data characteristics

1) What is measured and what is needed

Many techniques measure different property than what is actually needed. In such cases the needed property is computed out of raw data. The example can be GPR, which basically measures just time-depth response of signal in vertical measurement. In GPR technique there are always other signal coming from other directions – not only vertical. Such signals have to be removed by process called “migration”. The data which are used for interpretation and visualisation of GPR data are usually amplitudes of the response signal in gridded / raster space. An example of measured and wanted property can be also apparent resistivity and resistivity computed from it.

2) Negative, positive

There are both negative and positive values in geophysical or geochemical data. E.g. content of elements on soil is an example of values which can reach only positive values. The GPR data are usually visualised as amplitudes which can reach both positive and negative values.

3) Scalar, vector

Majority of the data used is of scalar character (pH, content of elements in soil; GPR – amplitudes of response signal). Nevertheless some of the methods can give data of vector characteristics – e.g. some seismic methods.

4) Qualitative, Quantitative – statistical characteristics

Majority of the data we are working with are represented by quantitative data, usually of continuous character.

Qualitative data can be also part of our analyses and they usually represent properties like soil type, geological background, archaeological dating and so on.

Figure 2. Where are our data from qualitative / quantitative point of view.

Some properties can be also described by both ways depending on methodology. Colour of the soil is an example of such property. It can be measured and represented in continuous quantitative way (e.g. CieLAB and so on), or in semi-quantitative / qualitative - ordinal way (Munsell), or purely in qualitative categories. It is also of great importance for the geophysical or geochemical characteristics as the colour is usually strongly influenced by them: e.g. reddish colour tones in cambisols or blueish/greenish colour tones in gleysols are the result of form of iron oxides (Fe^{3+} or Fe^{2+}).

5) Logarithmic data

Some of the data are inherently logarithmic. Typically it is the case of pH.

6) Compositional data; constrained data; open data

There are basically three types of data from this point of view. Open data means, that there are no dependency between variables in dataset and their numerical values can reach any values. Constrained data means that their sum has to be some constant value (usually 100 %). That means the values of variables in specific data point cannot reach any value, but are determined by other values. Such data cannot be analysed using usual statistical process (with presumption of randomness of the data).

Compositional data are similar to constrained, but there do not need to be any constant sum, but the data can be viewed as a part of some whole. Typical example is the geochemical data. This type of data can be statistically analysed using specific processes emphasising the relative relations among values – compositional data analysis.

As geochemical data – content of elements in soil – are typical example of compositional data, there was a question if geophysical data could be viewed as compositional. GPR data are usually visualised as raster maps. The values for raster cells are amplitudes and the raster itself is basically a matrix. Such data do not seem to be qualified as compositional data. Nevertheless the signal emitted from GPR is basically energy and the responses coming back are some parts of that energy. As data of GPR are usually presented as amplitudes, we have to re-compute the energy equivalent to those amplitudes (square of amplitudes). The second problem with GPR data is that the data are presented as matrix (2D array of one variable values). The compositional data can be applied only in cases where more variables are given – therefore the ratios between them can be processed. However, GPR data are basically comprised of many vertical measurements which are independent of the other. Therefore, vertical profile can be seen as one data point, in which the values are the parts of a whole. By this process it is possible to work with GPR data as compositional data – see also Figure 3 to illustrate the example.

Figure 3. Compositional character of GPR data. E is Energy, L is Loss, R is Response. The responses are parts of the whole: $E_0 = (E_1+E_2+E_3+\dots+E_n) + (L_1+L_2+L_3+\dots+L_n) + (R_1+R_2+R_3+\dots+R_n)$

7) Dimensionality of data - dimensionality of variables

As commented in part about compositional data, the dimensionality of the data is still question. Even one sample can give multidimensional data - the geochemical data are typical example. In some cases - as previously mentioned by GPR data, the dimensionality depends on how we perceive the data: typical GPR dataset of vertical profile can be viewed as univariate matrix of amplitudes. In such case, the dataset is 2D, but the data themselves are just 1D (one variable). But the same dataset can be viewed as a sequence of many vertical profiles independent on other. In such case (vertical profiles as data points), the dataset is 2D, but the data are nD - as many dimensions as number of horizontal layers.

3D data can be also produced by combination of more 2D measurements. Sometimes such process can produce discrepancies (e.g. 2D vertical profiles of TDIP perpendicular to each other can produce different values in area of their intersection).

F) Data types - datasets

1) Dimensionality of the dataset

This is different characteristic than dimensionality of measurement. Even 3D measurement (and GPR can be considered as 3D, or many 1D measurements - vertical profiles - located in 2D space...) can be stored as 3D array, or in form of many 2D matrices.

The dataset in this case (and its dimensionality) is therefore mainly product of data export or preparation for specific purpose of analysis or visualisation.

2) Types of storage

The storage of data has a file format aspect (which has a link to the topic of Accessibility of data) and data format aspect. The data can be stored in many ways: as graphics, as matrices, as data frames, vectors and so on.

3) *Accessibility of data*

Depending on device, manufacturer, software etc., in some cases raw numbers are not extractable from the measuring device.

Some methods and techniques use usual ways of storing the data, which are readable only in native software. To be read in other types of software, they have to be exported into different formats. GPR data can be an example of this: they are stored as binary data, in some cases the format is also producer / manufacturer dependent (e.g. rd3).

After the export, sometimes other processes have to be applied, e.g. rotation of exported matrix to get the vertical and horizontal directions right.

There is also a need to distinguish between data and readable data. This is not only question of data formats themselves (in which format data are stored) but also of format accessibility and time-durability – some formats get old and new softwares cannot read them. From this point of view, the most basic and simple formats are recommended for data storage.

G) Data types – categories of information characteristics

1) *Context dependency*

Does it make sense to obtain just one value of a property? Can it bear some information? Are there any methods / techniques, where the valuable information can be obtained only in placing all unique data points in the context of all others?

Michel Dabas: “geophysics is interested in anomalies”

- Therefore, the one value itself does not bear any usable information, its usage arises from the context of other values

We could state, that there are two types of contexts:

- Context by numbers – some patterns, information and so on can be revealed just by analysing the numbers
- Context by space – we need also the localization of the values to obtain information

2) *Graphical visualisation*

Many of the data have graphical visualisation (e.g. geophysical, aerial photography), but these data are usually just visualised rasters of numerical data in matrix format. Are there any data which format is primarily graphical – i.e. not visualisation of primarily numerical data?

3) *Dimensionality of graphical visualisation*

Majority of geophysical data is visualised in 2D dimension – vertical profiles or horizontal maps.